

#24

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

UNINTENDED IMPACTS MITIGATION

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING CREATING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At any stage in a project, foreseeing and mitigating unintended impacts.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to mid-sized multi-actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required, although brainstorming of unintended impacts (which may be unknown to actors) is required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1.5 -3 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials. At least one facilitator is required.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 11, 12.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Samuel Jeronimo on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- To identify possible unintended impacts.
- To facilitate participants to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions, which may lead to unintended impacts.
- To facilitate participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting plans.

Background and Logic

Due to the experimental nature of interactive innovation, its very nature and the processes involved can lead to unintended impacts. It is important for groups involved in interactive innovation to assess risks as well as benefits for unintended impacts to occur.

Tool #11 provides a tool to periodically assess and revise actions to ensure that the most beneficial impacts are achieved. This tool provides a tool to periodically assess the opposite: to appraise how unintended impacts may be occurring – particularly those identified as unwanted/sub-optimal from the perspectives of the actors involved. The tool facilitates actors to adjust/adapt/replace actions so that any unwanted/sub-optimal impacts may be prevented or mitigated.

Like Tool #11, this tool is inspired by [Gamble \(2018\)](#) as a reflexive tool for hypothesis building and re/generation. It is informed by a Developmental Evaluation approach where assumptions are challenged and hypotheses are revisited by adapting as the learning is carried out. Actual/emerging results, fact-checking and proofing is conducted using this reflexive tool. This tool allows participants to outline their goals and objectives but also allows them to continually revise and adapt their plans throughout the process.

This tool can be used with Tool #2, Tool #11, Tool #12, to build hypotheses for project tasks/actions and to reflexively revise tasks/actions.

Materials

- Flipchart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Sellotape
- Pre-printed headings

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1. Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the exercise.
- Hang up the completed hypotheses templates, generated by Tool#11

The hypotheses templates contain the following information for each task/action or cluster of tasks/actions:

- If we do.... (idea/task/action)
- Because.... (why?)
- We will get these results... (hypothesised)
- To achieve our goals/objectives... (impacts).

Step 2: Assessment of Hypotheses for Unintended Impacts

- Revisit-re-examine the ideas/tasks/actions for the project as a reminder to participants (originally identified by using Tool#2/Tool#11).
- Each actor (working alone) team of actors (working group) is assigned its own table and the tasks assigned to them in Tool#2/Tool#11 affixed to flipchart paper.

Step 4: Revision of Tasks/Actions

Each working group is then handed out a blank hypotheses template, again with the same headings:

- If we do.... (idea/task/action)
- Because.... (why?)
- We will get these results... (hypothesised)
- To achieve our goals/objectives... (impacts).

Participant/s at each table are asked to complete the blank hypotheses template, focusing specifically on whether they notice any *unintended, unwanted impacts emerging from the process*. The facilitator should walk around the room engaging with actor/s at the tables. Participants are then asked to revise any actions to avert or mitigate any unwanted, unintended aspect.

Traditional Approach (A) and a Developmental Evaluation Approach (B) (Gamble, 2018).

At the end of the workshop, the facilitator asks that one participant from each working group (or a single participant) present their revised plans. Facilitators ask that feedback is given to each group from the wider group. Assisting individual groups allows them to reflect on and re-evaluate (if necessary) their group plans.

Source: Gamble (2018)

Step 5: Continuous Reflexivity

As the participants continue through the process of interactive innovation, ensure that they are facilitated to continuously re-assess, update and revise group plans as required at further workshops/meetings. This encourages participants to think reflexively while also allowing participants to be in control of the decisions, adapting or revising their plans at any stage, avoiding or mitigating any unwanted, unintended impacts.

